

08 – TRACING MOISTURE SOURCES AND SINKS OF FIVE EXCEPTIONAL IRISH LANDFALLING ATMOSPHERIC RIVERS

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Abstract

Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) are thin filaments of moisture that flow through the lower troposphere from the tropics and sub-tropics towards the upper latitudes. When ARs make landfall and interact with different terrain, they are often associated with heavy precipitation and flood events. Ireland lies in the path of ARs in the North Atlantic region and is subject to a spectrum of landfalling AR events per year, with impacts ranging from beneficial to hazardous. In this study, two global AR databases are used to identify ARs that made landfall over Ireland for a 20-year study period, 2002 - 2021. Met Éireann's gridded high-resolution precipitation dataset for Ireland is used to find country-wide extreme precipitation. By correlating the AR entry-exit dates over Ireland with the extreme daily precipitation dates, it is found that 86% (146 out of 169) of the events were associated with AR occurrences. Subsequently, five intense AR-associated and five non-AR associated synoptic-scale extreme precipitation events are selected for moisture source and sink analysis. Then, 10-day back-trajectory analysis is conducted to track moisture histories of the selected events using NOAA's Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model followed by Lagrangian moisture diagnostics for analysis. AR events reveal significant moisture from subtropical and remote regions such as the Sargasso Sea, western and central North Atlantic, and even the Pacific. In contrast, non-AR events show higher fraction of trajectories and sources/sink regions surrounding Ireland and eastern North Atlantic, such as the adjacent North, Irish, Celtic, and Baltic Seas. Results show that hazardous ARs which lead to extreme precipitation in Ireland can be traced to their moisture source regions and can be associated with large-scale teleconnections and weather patterns. To expand scientific understanding and to improve flood forecasting in Ireland, it is recommended to further explore the origins and climatic conditions of the moisture source regions of ARs.

1. INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric rivers (ARs) can be described as thin plumes of moisture or water vapor transport in the lower troposphere, moving towards upper latitudes (or poles) from tropical sources (Newell et al., 1992; Zhu and Newell, 1998). Typically, the movement of this vertically integrated water vapor (IVT) occurs through atmospheric winds such as the low-level jet stream ahead of a cold front of a midlatitude cyclone. This low-level jet acts as a conveyor belt for the horizontal movement of vapor (Gimeno et al., 2014; Prince et al., 2021). Recent studies found that there are seven to ten ARs at any given time globally, and they are responsible for transporting 90% of the total poleward moisture (Guan and Waliser, 2015; Martin Ralph et al., 2019).

ARs are a common phenomenon on the western coasts of Europe and North America in the northern hemisphere (Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Martin Ralph et al., 2019). Large island nations, such as Ireland, receive a variety of weak to strong ARs every year, more frequently in autumn and winter seasons

(Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Lavers et al., 2012). Heavy to extreme precipitation often follows AR events when they make landfall in Ireland and neighboring coastal nations (Champion et al., 2015; Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Gleeson et al., 2019).

There have been major improvements in AR detection and tracking technology since Zhu and Newell's landmark study in the early 1990s (Gleeson et al., 2019). Due to the availability of modern sub-daily reanalysis data, such as MERRA2, ERA5, and JRA55, it is now possible to create extensive global datasets of AR events using AR detection tools (ARDTs). Notably, countless global and regional studies have been conducted using ARDTs over the years (Guan and Waliser, 2024; Prince et al., 2021). Multiple ARDTs have been applied to polar regions, such as Antarctica, Greenland, and other remote areas, through which these detection tools were improved and calibrated for better accuracy and AR tracking capabilities (Guan and Waliser, 2024; Mattingly et al., 2018; Wille et al., 2025).

Due to various methodologies used by different ARDTs (such as threshold-based, geometry-based, Eulerian-based object tracking etc.) and multiple reanalysis input datasets, there are uncertainties and variations in detected ARs (Lora et al., 2020). To address the issues of AR detection using large reanalysis datasets and robustness of the ARDTs, the Atmospheric River Tracking Method Intercomparison Project (ARTMIP) has been established to test ARDTs and intercompare their capabilities to quantify AR characteristics and detection accuracy (Collow et al., 2022). However, since different ARDTs produce varying results, it is important to apply these algorithms regionally and site-specific applications are then used to understand global nuances (Prince et al., 2021).

One widely used ARDT for both global and regional applications is called the Tracking Atmospheric Rivers Globally as Elongated Targets (tARget) algorithm, previously known as GW15 (Guan and Waliser, 2024; Prince et al., 2021). Most ARDTs use AR identification to detect ARs based on AR characteristics at one location, which is a Eulerian-based method. In contrast, tARget takes a step further and uses a Lagrangian method of tracking the AR over time and space from genesis to termination (Guan and Waliser, 2024). Although ARDTs answer key questions about ARs, crucial details about the moisture sources and sinks of ARs can be further investigated by moisture transport tracking tools.

Wernli and Davies (1997) laid the groundwork for Lagrangian-based analysis of moisture transport and used numerous in long range moisture studies and moisture residence times since then (Wernli and Davies, 1997). Moisture tracking tools in modern times, based on Lagrangian and Eulerian approaches, have been employed to track moisture transport pathways and pin-point source regions to discover the origins of extreme precipitation (Pérez-Alarcón et al., 2025). For instance, Stohl (2008), conducted a Lagrangian-based study of remote sources of water vapor responsible for precipitation in Bergen, Norway. They found that tropical and sub-tropical warm regions which are subject to higher rates of evaporation are responsible for heavy precipitation in upper latitudes regions. The moisture is usually brought to the Norwegian west coast through long-distance transport mechanisms such as ARs (Stohl et al., 2008).

In previous studies, AR influence has been identified for Britain and linked with extreme precipitation and flooding events for both extended winter and summer periods (Champion et al., 2015; Lavers et al., 2011). For Ireland, a study has been conducted to identify persistent ARs and their association with

extreme precipitation, also AR seasonal variability was examined (Gleeson et al., 2019). More recently, Eiras-Barca et al. (2021) modified the global AR ranking system to fit to the European west-coast and did regional estimates for AR ranks (1-5) reaching Ireland and Britain (Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Martin Ralph et al., 2019). However, landfalling ARs in Ireland are yet to be studied for its entire lifecycle and their moisture origins, sources, and sinks along the way are unexplored.

In this study, top five Irish AR-associated extreme precipitation events and non-AR extreme events are selected from 20-year period and investigated for determining their moisture source and sink regions. Using global AR databases, landfalling ARs are identified and correlated with precipitation events with Ireland-wide average daily precipitation beyond the 95th percentile threshold. Afterwards, back-trajectory analysis using the HYSPLIT software is performed for tracking moisture along the path of AR and non-AR events. One key component of the study is using an established Lagrangian moisture source and sink detection methodology (Sodemann et al., 2008) which revealed Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) and above-PBL moisture attribution for accurate assignment of source and sink regions.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Atmospheric River (AR) and AR ranks detection

The variable Integrated Water Vapor Transport (IVT) is the dominant variable widely used to detect ARs. **Equation (i)** shows how the IVT (in kg/m/s) is calculated using meteorological data from different pressure levels from the surface (1000 hpa) to the top of the troposphere ($\approx 300 - 100$ hpa) depending on the altitude (Z) and moist air density (ρ) Typically, specific humidity (q), eastward and northward wind components (u, v), and acceleration due to gravity (g) are key meteorological variables which are required to obtain IVT. However, modern reanalysis products already provide eastward and northward components of integrated water vapor flux (Q_u, Q_v) to obtain the resultant vector,

$$IVT \text{ (kg/m/s)} = \sqrt{Q_u^2 + Q_v^2}, (Q_u, Q_v) = \int_0^{Z_{top}} (u, v) \rho q dz = \frac{1}{g} \int_{P_{300}}^{P_{1000}} (u, v) q dp \dots (i)$$

The tARget V4 ARDT developed and updated by Guan and Waliser (2024) is selected for this study for its Lagrangian AR tracking at 6h time steps and advanced identification capabilities based on IVT and geometric characteristics such as the length to width ratio (Guan and Waliser, 2024). TARget V4 is powered by the ERA5 reanalysis meteorological data by ECMWF and generates a high-resolution output of 0.25° horizontal resolution at 6-hour intervals (Hersbach et al., 2020). The output file from the algorithm is made available by Guan (2024) at dataverse.ucla.edu/dataverse and consists of a global database of AR events from 1940 to 2025 (Guan, 2024). From the database the frequency of unique landfalling ARs over Ireland is extracted alongside their characteristics such as mean IVT, length, width, AR axis (direction), landfalling location, AR dates and duration over Ireland.

A separate dataset (<https://dataverse.ucla.edu/dataverse/ar>) is available for global AR ranks based on the tARget V3 algorithm by Guan (2021) and creates a database based on the AR scales methodology developed by Ralph (2019). ARs are categorized as beneficial to hazardous using a 5-point scale. The weakest AR1 is classified with a maximum IVT ≥ 250 kg/m/s at a given location and a duration ≥ 24 h, whereas an exceptional AR5 has a maximum IVT ≥ 1250 kg/m/s and typically a duration ≥ 48 h (Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Martin Ralph et al., 2019). AR2-4 lies between other duration and IVT thresholds (refer to Ralph et al., 2019). The scales database is fed using the MERRA2 reanalysis meteorological

data by NASA and produces an output of $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$ horizontal resolution every 6-h time step (Guan et al., 2023). This AR scales database is primarily used to detect the ranks of ARs entering and leaving Ireland. These ARs are then correlated with the landfalling ARs from the global database to find exceptional and hazardous ARs, their maximum IVT values, and IVT total for the entire AR object, and maximum duration.

2.2 Precipitation data

Met Éireann's high-resolution Irish gridded precipitation dataset is used to assess extreme precipitation associated with AR events. The dataset used is publicly available at <https://www.met.ie/daily-rainfall-and-temperature-grids> for a period of 1941 to 2024. The points are placed on 1 km by 1 km Irish grid system (TM65) distance and covers the entire land area of Ireland. The gridded dataset is created using daily rainfall totals values from approximately five hundred observation stations. The data is standardized by using regression analysis to identify key variables that influence the observation dataset (such as distance to the coast for coastal effects) and created detrended data for interpolation. Interpolation techniques such as Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) and Kriging were used on the available station data. Further explanations on the gridded datasets can be found in the climatological reports by Walsh (2016) and Coonan et al. (2024) on the Met Éireann website (Coonan et al., 2024; Walsh, 2016).

In this study, the gridded data are downloaded for the 20-year period from 2002 to 2021. The data is averaged for each day for all the grid points covering Ireland and a country-wide daily average value is obtained for each day of the entire period. A lower threshold of 2.54 mm is applied to the average daily values to identify only wet days based on a methodology developed by Rutz (2014). Afterwards, an upper threshold of 95th percentile is applied to the days crossing the lower threshold to obtain an upper threshold value for the entire dataset. This is a simplified method developed using studies using peak-over-threshold values to determine extreme precipitation (Champion et al., 2015; Gleeson et al., 2019; Rutz et al., 2014). Only those days having a daily average value crossing the upper threshold (15.58 mm/day) are extreme precipitation days (like “very wet days” indicator by Ryan et al., 2022).

The extreme days identified are then correlated with landfalling AR durations over Ireland, where AR and non-AR extreme precipitation days are separated. The top 5 AR and non-AR rainfall days are then selected based on daily average total precipitation values for this study. To ensure that country-wide extreme rainfall days are considered, only the days that have 60% of the grid points crossing the 95th percentile thresholds are considered in addition to the absolute daily value.

In addition to the precipitation data, two climate classifications are used to identify the weather for selected days: i. Lamb's weather types based on the Jenkinson modified scheme (Jenkinson and Collison, 1977; Lamb, 1972). The NCEP-NCAR (Kalnay et al., 1996) reanalysis-based data collected for the selected days can be found here: <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/data/lwt>, and ii. The daily North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) index values, collected from the NCEP website: <https://ftp.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/cwlinks/>.

2.3 Moisture sources and sinks classification

Sodemann (2008), in their foundational study of Lagrangian moisture source diagnostics methodology, proposed that specific humidity (q) values in an air parcel along a pathway can be used to determine precipitation and evaporation effects (Sodemann et al., 2008). Originally developed by

James (2004) and Stohl (2004), this methodology shows how either precipitation or evaporation is dominant over any 6-hour time step (James et al., 2004; Stohl and James, 2004). Moving backwards from the moisture arrival point, at every timestep moisture change is noted (+q change for evaporation and -q change for precipitation). When the moisture uptake is considered, a fraction is calculated based on the current q at that timestep. For every location where precipitation occurs, a fraction is deducted from the uptakes in the previous step, reducing the overall moisture uptake fraction (Akers et al., 2020; Molina and Allen, 2019; Sodemann et al., 2008).

Moisture uptake threshold values range from 0.1 to 0.2 g/kg for numerous studies (Fremme and Sodemann, 2019; Sodemann, 2020; Sodemann et al., 2008). Usually, for higher latitudes a lower threshold is required, and the opposite is true for tropical and subtropical regions (Sodemann, 2025). In this study, a 3-hour higher resolution dataset is used as opposed to the original 6-hour dataset in Sodemann (2008), so the lower threshold of 0.1 g/kg is selected to consider evaporation. The threshold for sinks is set as a dual criterion: 1. -0.1 g/kg removal from the specific humidity, and 2. a relative humidity of > 80%, as it ensures that precipitation conditions are met (Fremme and Sodemann, 2019; Sodemann et al., 2008) The change in moisture considered above are subdivided into PBL attribution (where moisture is from traceable surface sources, f_{tot}), above-PBL attribution (e_{tot}), and unknown attribution (d_{tot}).

Met Éireann's daily precipitation dataset is based on the 9 am to 9 am UTC (24-h) sample collection times. So, the total precipitation amount for one day is being measured at 9 am the day after and assigned to the date before (Walsh, 2016). To match these times, the trajectory starting times are placed at 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 0, 3, 6, 9-hour time steps to match the extreme precipitation meteorological day and extra 3 hours as buffer time. The starting locations of the trajectories are selected to be the latitudes and longitudes at the maximum precipitation.

Lagrangian backward trajectory tools require the user to specify trajectory height(s) as starting positions. Some studies use specific (10, 100, 200, 500 m etc.) starting heights to capture the air parcels at different levels (Akers et al., 2020; Sodemann et al., 2008). Several aircraft and satellite data-based studies based in both North American and European west coasts suggest that 950 hpa – 700 hpa pressure levels (corresponding to 500 – 3000 m above ground level) are where 75% of the AR moisture is found (Lavers et al., 2020; Ralph et al., 2017). In this study, trajectory starting heights of 500, 1500, and 2500 m (\approx 950, 850, and 750 hpa) above ground levels are selected to capture surface-level moisture transport, core AR transport pathway, and AR-top or mid-tropospheric transport pathways.

The PBL and the turbulent mixing layer depth (MLD) inside the PBL varies diurnally, seasonally, and due to other surface processes such as heating, cooling, wind movement, etc. GDAS underestimates the MLD during anti-cyclonic and cyclonic conditions. AR and synoptic-scale precipitation events are directly connected to these conditions, and it is assumed that models (e.g., HYSPLIT) produce underestimated MLD outputs during these times (Julaha et al., 2025). So, a safety factor is introduced in the classification for below PBL height consideration for moisture source regions. Sodemann (2008) uses a 1.5 safety factor on top of the boundary layer height to account for the underestimation by ERA dataset (Sodemann et al., 2008). Since AR moisture transport is the primary focus and given the marine sources surrounding Ireland, a scaling factor of 1.75 is used to account for model, seasonal, diurnal, and regional underestimations.

2.4 HYSPLIT back-trajectory analysis

The Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model is NOAA Air Resources Laboratory's principal atmospheric transport and dispersion model, with over three decades of model development (Draxler and Hess, 1998; Stein et al., 2015; available at <https://www.arl.noaa.gov/hysplit>). The model uses a Lagrangian framework of spatial and temporal interpolation of velocity vectors of an air parcel on top of a Eulerian fixed grid system (Draxler and Hess, 1998). This helps track air transport pathways at different timesteps while using Eulerian 3D meteorological gridded data to conduct interpolations between timesteps. HYSPLIT incorporates this in its advection algorithm so that moisture amounts at each timestep can be calculated and tracked alongside other variables.

In this study, to run the HYSPLIT model, the 1°-degree horizontal resolution meteorological product by National Centers for Atmospheric Prediction's (NCEP) Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS) archived data is used. This is a 3-h temporal resolution dataset which consists of key variables for the HYSPLIT model, such as relative humidity, eastward and northward winds, temperature, planetary boundary height, global radiation, etc. Notice that each dataset used in this study has a different spatial and temporal resolution, so the values obtained through the results should be cautiously read and only be considered as percentages or proportions.

Next, to conduct multiple trajectory analysis with different locations, times, and iterations, the SplitR package (by Rich Iannone, [description](#)) is used on R-studio. The package is validated by back-trajectory and pollutant dispersion studies (e.g., Gustafsson et al., 2010), and it is featured on NOAA's ARL HYSPLIT website for integration with R (<https://www.ready.noaa.gov/HYSPLIT.php>). The trajectory starting times, heights, and locations discussed above are set in the SplitR R script. The commonly used 10-day backward trajectory time is selected for the study, which will allow moisture to be tracked before the genesis of the selected ARs (Akers et al., 2020; Baldini et al., 2010). The moisture source regions are assigned using latitude and longitude bounding boxes for 66 geographical areas and will be assigned to grid cells with significant E-P moisture fluxes. The major regions are the Arctic seas, North Atlantic, North Pacific, Mediterranean regions, and several land regions like Britain and continental Europe.

2.5 Model sensitivity

Key variables in Lagrangian backwards trajectory modelling are trajectory starting heights, planetary boundary layer selection for moisture region identification, moisture uptake and loss thresholds, and backwards trajectory lengths (Sodemann et al., 2008). These variables are tested for sensitivity analysis and optimal variables are selected in alignment with the literature.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 ARs and extreme precipitation

From the global AR dataset (Guan, 2024), 1600 distinct AR events passed over Ireland in the period 2002 to 2021. TARget ARDT classifies landfalling ARs as those that intersect the coastline (overlapping the land mask) by a minimum of 1-grid, AR axis is directed towards the land or onshore, and majority of the AR length (>1000) must be on the ocean. Only then, the maximum IVT grid which intersects with the land is thus labelled as the landfall location. Among the 1600 ARs detected, 913 of them are

considered to have made landfall over Ireland by the algorithm. The rest are not considered major ARs for Ireland in this study, as they are either too transient or made landfall elsewhere. **Figure 1 (a-e)** shows the top 5 selected ARs between 2002 - 2021 during their landfall in Ireland, alongside their characteristics and ranks (**f-j**) (Guan, 2024; Guan, 2023).

To be considered an AR, the length to width ratio of the object needs to be 2 or greater. The top 5 ARs are exceptional, as they are longer in size than average, with the smallest length (**Figure 1.a**) being 5.8 times the width of the AR object. Other traits of the 5 ARs are shown in the AR rank maps (**Figure 1.f-j**), where maximum IVT detected are in the range of 1000 - 1400 kg/m/s approximately, which are considered above the 99th percentile in AR climatological studies (Prince et al., 2021). Moreover, the top 5 ARs have the highest ranks of 4 – 5, heavy rainfall and flooding are often associated with these ranks and are classified as hazardous (Eiras-Barca et al., 2021; Martin Ralph et al., 2019). In addition, duration analysis show that these ARs spent 30 – 84 hours (5 – 14 timesteps) over land during their passing, covering 70 – 87% of Ireland's land area.

Since AR events are synoptic in nature, they span across global to local scales due to synoptic scale air circulations. To understand the synoptic origins of the selected AR events, the Lamb's Weather Type (LWT) values are extracted to see their airflow types. LWTs are circulation classifications for Ireland and Britain, having 7 principal circulation types and 27 subdivisions (Sweeney, 1985; Lamb, 1972). The selected ARs have circulations classified as Figure 1. a South Westerly, b. Southerly, c. South Westerly, d. South Westerly, and e. Southerly. The LWTs match with the direction of the AR axes shown in Figure 1, having south westerly and southerly transport pathways over Ireland.

LWT conditions can be explained using the North Atlantic teleconnection pressure differences which modulates the position of the storm pathways in the region (Eiras-Barca et al., 2018). The NAO index helps quantify the variability of sea-level pressure changes between the Icelandic low cyclonic and Azores high anti-cyclonic systems (Hurrell, 1995). The NAO values associated with the first 4 ARs (**Figure 1.a-d**) are in between 0.69 – 2.47, whereas the last AR date (**Figure 1.e**) shows a daily value of -1.32. NAO+ values imply strong westerly, having a strong pressure gradient which drives the Atlantic storm track north, and in contrast NAO- implies strong easterly winds (HURRELL and VAN LOON, 1997). This can be further corroborated by **Figure 1** which shows the last AR (**1.f**) shifting towards the northwest after making landfall in Ireland.

Landfalling ARs tend to bring extreme precipitation totals and risks of flooding due to their moisture rich characteristics, having orographic effects on mountainous terrains in Ireland and Britain (Gleeson et al., 2019; Lavers and Villarini, 2013). When extreme precipitation days are selected and correlated with AR dates and duration in Ireland (refer to **Section 2**), it is found that 146 out of 169 extreme events occur on AR days in the 20-year study period. The remaining 21 extreme events does not fall on AR days. The top 5 selected AR-associated and non-AR extreme precipitation events are shown in **Figure 2 (a-e. AR events and f-j. non-AR events)**. From here on these event dates will be called "AR precip 1 – 5" and "non-AR precip 1 – 5" sequentially.

Differing from AR-associated LWTs mentioned above, the non-AR precipitation events are associated with the circulations: 1. South Easterly, 2. Cyclonic, 3. South Westerly, 4. Cyclonic, and 5. Cyclonic (**Figure 2. f-j**). These circulation types are supported by their NAO index values, where 4 non-AR days (**Figure 2.f, g, h, and j**) show negative NAO values between -0.95 to -0.17. Only non-AR precip 4 (**Figure**

2.i) show a weak positive value of 0.43. NAO- values suggest easterly and northerly air flow, having anti-cyclonic systems forming across Scandinavia to Iceland, and cyclonic systems moving from the Biscay to western North Atlantic (Hurrell, 1995; Sweeney, 1985).

Noticeably, the top AR days (**Figure 2.a-e**) exhibit higher country-wide average precipitation totals (29.5 – 36.1 mm/day) and maximum precipitation totals (91.5 – 160.8 mm/day) compared to non-AR days. One explanation for this is the southerly/south-westerly LWTs and NAO+ values associated with the ARs, which correspond to blocking anticyclones in northern-central Europe and slow-moving depressions near Ireland (Hurrell, 1995; Sweeney, 1985). This setup leads to elongated downpours and are known to produce the highest rainfall totals, especially in the southern highlands of Ireland due to orographic influences (Sweeney, 1985; Sweeney and O’Hare, 1992). This is consistent with AR research, where extended winter periods (September – February) observe annual maxima precipitation in northern Europe due to exceptional ARs such as the ones selected for this study (Lavers and Villarini, 2013).

Since ARs are associated with mean westerly flow from the North Atlantic, beyond the NAO and LWTs, studies have linked the mid-latitude jet stream and large-scale weather regimes to be responsible for landfalling AR events in north-western Europe in the extended winter (Lavers and Villarini, 2013; Pasquier et al., 2019). Particularly, “Zonal” weather regime (jet stream moving west-east, parallel to latitude lines) presents an airflow configuration that increases AR frequency in Ireland and an enhanced likelihood of extreme precipitation totals (Pasquier et al., 2019). For non-AR extreme events, the “Atlantic Trough” and “Scandinavian Blocking” regimes, which bring possibilities of cyclonic systems in the region and can be responsible for extraordinary precipitation in Ireland. These weather regimes can help explain the cyclonic LWT, southerly/westerly LWT, and NAO phases found in the non-AR and AR extreme days selected for this study.

Figure 1: Maps illustrating the top 5 Irish AR events selected for the study and their global AR scale maps during landfall. AR events are categorized by their duration, intensity (IVT), and geometry. To assess ARs and their associated impacts, it is important to measure these key characteristics and find landfall locations. Here, **a-e** show the ERA5 global database AR shapes, axis, and important characteristics such as mean IVT and geometry. **f-j**. Global ranks (AR 1-5) of the selected AR events based on the MERRA2 AR scale dataset, maximum IVT and duration detected over Ireland. Note that since ARs are ranked/categorized based on their maximum IVTs, in this case each grid cell (AR points) has their own rank. The maximum ranked grid that passes over Ireland is the rank assigned to that AR. In this case, the 5 AR events in Ireland receives the following ranks: **f**. AR rank 4, **g**. AR rank 4, **h**. AR rank 4, **j**. AR rank 5, and **j**. AR rank 4. Data source: Guan (2024) and Guan (2023).

Figure 2: Bivariate maps showing daily precipitation distribution against the elevation of Ireland for selected AR (a-e) and non-AR (f-j) events. These maps show that AR events generate the maximum precipitation close to their landfall locations and in the elevated coastal areas of Ireland due to orographic effect. In contrast, non-AR events display wider land coverage of precipitation even in low-lying areas of Ireland. For each event, the country-wide average total and maximum total precipitation values for 24 hours are written in the subtitle of each individual map. The diamond points (yellow) show the maximum total precipitation grid point for that event. Importantly, these points are selected as starting locations for the HYSPLIT back-trajectory analysis for each event. Data source: Met Éireann’s daily gridded precipitation data.

3.2 Moisture source and sink regions

Kinematic backwards trajectory is executed using the SplitR package for HYSPLIT on R for the 1 * 1 grid air parcels from the maximum precipitation location sites on **Figure 2**, for 5 AR and non-AR precipitation event days. Each 5 AR and 5 non-AR runs resulted into 135 unique trajectories (27 per event) and 10,935 trajectory points based on 9 starting times (9am to 9 am UTC meteorological day), 3-hour intervals, 3 above ground starting heights, and 10-day (240h) length backward trajectories. For AR events, 1,026 PBL, 1,135 above-PBL source events (2,161 in total), and 1,175 sink events are detected. Non-AR events analysis resulted in 1,444 PBL and 1,053 above-PBL source events (2,497 in total), and 1,354 sink events. In both cases, the source events are detected twice as much as sink events.

Figure 3 (a-c. AR events and d-f. non-AR events) are showing trajectory, moisture source, and moisture sink Kernel Density Estimation plots based on their probability of occurrence in the grid cells. This method is used to identify hot regions for trajectories, sources, and sinks where overlapping kernels are summed together for visualization based on density. For instance, bright colours point towards higher densities whereas darker shades of purple/blue are showing fewer trajectory points. **Figure 3** highlights clear distinctions between AR and non-AR precipitation air parcels.

For AR events, directions of trajectories (**3.a**) are dominantly from the west and southwest of Ireland. There is a higher density hotspot between central to western North Atlantic, indicating that all 5 AR events have air parcels travelling from this area. In contrast, the non-AR trajectories (**3.d**) show denser areas in all directions near Ireland, showing equally dense areas from North America, continental Europe, and the Norwegian Sea. Notably, the AR events show trajectories reaching further south, having relatively dense spots over Africa, sub-tropics, the Gulf of Mexico, and pacific regions.

The moisture source densities (**3.b, e**) display all the source events (both PBL and above-PBL) detected and the brighter areas are where the source events are overlapping most frequently. From the sources detected, trajectory statistics show that 48% (for AR events) and 60% (for non-AR events) of the uptakes are found to be from below the PBL on average and are traceable to their source regions. In **Figure 3.b**, the densest regions for AR events are from central to eastern North Atlantic and having significant densities spread across eastern North America. In comparison, non-AR events show denser moisture uptake surrounding Ireland, Celtic Sea, Irish Sea, and the North Sea. The further the distance from Ireland, the paler the densities become relative to AR sources.

The sink regions show distinct differences between AR and non-AR events. With bright hotspots in the central North Atlantic and surrounding North Atlantic regions for AR events, and the clear densest region is in the east of Ireland for non-AR events, around the North Sea. Like source events, the AR sink regions stretch out further in remote areas such as the western North America, which decreases the importance of remote source regions as precipitation removes earlier sources along the path. In comparison, non-AR sources and sink hotspots are closer and often overlapping, showing that uptake and loss happen in proximity and nearer to Ireland.

Table 1 summarises key insights about the total source against sinks data obtained from the back-trajectory analysis, a simplified version of James (2004) evaporation – precipitation diagnostics (James et al., 2004). It shows the number of grid cells, mean evaporation and precipitation event percentages

based on the total number of events, and most importantly the net flux of moisture (E-P) from the top 10 regions.

Figure 3: The maps visualize the extent of HYSPLIT backward trajectories, moisture sources (e.g., evaporation), and sinks (e.g., precipitation) along the 10-day back-trajectory lengths using density maps. Raw trajectories and moisture sources and sink points are spread across the map domain and often overlapping one another. These density maps make the visualization less obscure and are used to see different trajectory pathways and hotspots for sources and sinks between (a-c) AR events and (d-f) non-AR events. Here, their densities are calculated using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) and are normalized to a scale of 0 – 1.

When total sources (PBL + above-PBL) and sinks are compared, such as in **Table 1**, central North Atlantic region show the most amount of grid cells and the number of uptake/loss events for both AR

and non-AR events. This quantifies the densities shown in **Figure 3**. In addition, the net flux reveals the regions where sink events are stronger than all source events. For AR events, the net flux shows that evaporation and moisture gaining along the trajectories outweigh precipitation and moisture losses for all the top 10 regions. However, for non-AR events, the near areas show greater moisture flux. The North Sea being the biggest sink and the Celtic Sea (or the atmosphere above) is the most significant source of moisture for non-AR events.

Table 1: Number of source and sink events in terms of evaporation and precipitation events detected for AR and non-AR events. The net flux shows the E-P of the top 10 contributing regions in the back-trajectory analysis.

AR associated events						
Region	Grid Cells	Source Events	Sink Events	Avg E %	Avg P %	Net Flux (g/kg)
Central North Atlantic	379	465	501	34.2	65.8	39.0
North America East	297	327	87	73.9	26.1	70.7
Subtropical North Atlantic	194	165	131	49.7	50.3	13.5
Western North Atlantic	155	192	69	64.6	35.4	22.2
North America West	151	146	39	76.0	24.0	50.6
Other Atlantic	100	91	53	68.5	31.5	1.8
North Pacific Central	107	88	26	75.8	24.2	18.2
Eastern North Atlantic	27	80	26	53.1	46.9	46.5
Celtic Sea	27	87	17	62.0	38.0	22.4
Bay of Biscay	18	61	28	51.0	49.0	14.4
Non-AR associated events						
Region	Grid Cells	Source Events	Sink Events	Avg E %	Avg P %	Net Flux (g/kg)
Central North Atlantic	347	431	233	54.5	45.5	8.0
North Sea	128	339	202	44.5	55.5	-23.9
Celtic Sea	51	337	97	56.5	43.5	95.6
North America East	212	172	118	56.4	43.6	2.4
Western North Atlantic	139	122	99	43.9	56.1	-22.1
Eastern North Atlantic	61	131	50	56.3	43.7	5.0
Norwegian Sea	102	86	62	44.2	55.8	-9.7
Subtropical North Atlantic	108	102	40	67.8	32.2	14.1
Labrador Sea	87	48	84	31.6	68.4	-4.7
Subpolar North Atlantic	88	83	47	60.2	39.8	2.6

The trajectories further clarify that remote sources play a vital role in AR moisture transport and even if moisture is lost along the way, trace fractions of those remote moistures still reach Ireland. This further shows the strength of the synoptic-scale weather regimes, where Zonal jet stream patterns allow evenly distributed depressions for this moisture to transport long distances. Also, non-AR sources show strong characteristics of cyclonic events as nearer moisture rises in the turbulent mixing layer below the PBL and precipitates. This further corroborates the LWTs and NAO- phases seen in the previous section.

The atmosphere receives majority of the water vapour through turbulent exchanges near the surface, below the PBL (Arya, 2001). To accurately trace moisture back towards its source regions, an air parcel in the back-trajectory needs to be below the PBL, where turbulent fluxes help the parcel exchange moisture (Sodemann et al., 2008). Moreover, Sodemann (2008) emphasized that above-PBL moisture cannot be assigned to a particular evaporation source, because that air could be mixed from other air parcels or below cloud evaporation, convection or numerical errors can also occur (Sodemann et al.,

2008). Therefore, below PBL moisture source fractions are separated from above-PBL source and unknown fractions (e.g., existing water in the parcel before back-trajectory length). The mean PBL (f_{tot}), above-PBL (e_{tot}), and unknown attribution (d_{tot}) source percentages arriving to Ireland in the starting location are shown in **Table 2** for individual AR and non-AR events.

In their foundational study, Sodemann (2008) found that on average 66% precipitation can be attributed to evaporative sources (f_{tot}) derived from hundreds of thousands of trajectories for 30 different months. This number widely varied between individual trajectories and events. Similarly, for above-PBL sources and unknown attribution between 10 – 30% (e_{tot}) and less than 20% (d_{tot}) sources were found in most cases (Sodemann et al., 2008). These fractions, especially for below PBL moisture varies largely due to mix depth layer considerations and underestimations according to Sodemann (2008). Also, this is found to be the case in this study where higher PBL thresholds increased PBL attribution, decreased above-PBL percentages, but the unknown remained the same.

Table 2: Average Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL), above-PBL, and unknown moisture attributions for each AR and non-AR precipitation event locations in Ireland.

Site	PBL - Ftot (%)	Above-PBL - Etot (%)	Unknown - Dtot (%)
AR precip 1	35.6	56.8	7.6
AR precip 2	53.3	31.2	15.5
AR precip 3	49.4	39.3	11.3
AR precip 4	40.3	53.2	6.6
AR precip 5	39.1	54.8	6.0
Non-AR precip 1	59.8	35.8	4.4
Non-AR precip 2	53.4	32.3	14.3
Non-AR precip 3	67.2	30.2	2.6
Non-AR precip 4	58.4	30.9	10.8
Non-AR precip 5	39.1	55.7	5.1

In this study, the AR precipitations resulted into an average PBL moisture attribution to be 43.5% from 135 trajectories for the 5 events. Individual events having estimates between 35.6% to 53%. While the above-PBL sources are between 31.2% – 56.8%, the unknown percentages are less than 16%. Non-AR events displayed higher PBL attributions from 39.1% - 67.2%, and lower unknown attribution compared to AR events (see **Table 1**). These percentages can be ascribed to a mixture of thresholds selection, trajectory starting heights, and other model parameters, as well as to the NAO phase setup, LWTs, and weather regimes.

For instance, during model sensitivity, it is seen that near ground starting heights tend to capture higher PBL moisture attributions. Sodemann (2008) uses ground level elevations (approx. 2000 m above sea level), whereas in this study 500 – 2500 m above ground level is used to capture AR moisture hotspots. This captures more above-PBL moistures along the trajectories. Another important consideration is the back-trajectory length. Although Sodemann (2008) used 20-day lengths, newer studies show that approx. 5-15 days explain evaporative sources of precipitation depending on

different regions (Läderach and Sodemann, 2016). Sensitivity testing showed lower unknown attributions for longer trajectory days (15-day) and higher PBL in Non-AR and higher above-PBL attributions in AR events. However, numerical errors may arise and accrue over time as trajectory lengths are increased, so the 10-day length results are considered for this study.

Figure 4 shows the below PBL moisture source grids which contributed to the precipitation at trajectory starting locations in Ireland. Different colours are used to identify only AR, non-AR, and overlapping grids which contribute to both type of events. Noticeably, only non-AR grids are denser towards the northeast of Ireland with subpolar to polar regions contributing during the extreme precipitation events. This is characteristic of the cyclonic weather type, weak NAO-, and consequent Atlantic Trough causing a low-pressure system to persist in the central North Atlantic which circulates moisture over Ireland from close proximities (Lavers and Villarini, 2013; Sweeney, 1985).

Overlapping grids in yellow show the significant spatial influence of central and eastern North Atlantic regions for extreme precipitation in Ireland during both AR and non-AR events. In the overlapping grids, AR events have higher source contributions indicating these regions to be important for AR moisture uptake compared to non-AR events. Only AR grid cells roughly follow the westerly pathways associated with upper-level Jet Streams in the mid-latitudes during Zonal regimes (Woollings et al., 2010). This synoptic pattern couples itself with low-level Jets and intensifies them by pulling moisture, which can be an explanation as to why the AR events are strong (Eiras-Barca et al., 2018; Uccellini and Johnson, 1979).

Figure 4: Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) moisture sources contributing to the final precipitation arriving in Ireland locations. The 1*1 resolution grid cells are distributed for AR, non-AR, and overlapping (both AR and non-AR) regions.

Additional event-wise PBL attribution reveal that, besides central and eastern North Atlantic, subtropical North Atlantic, Sargasso Sea, Bay of Biscay, and further remote regions in the Pacific and western North America contributed significantly to AR precipitation events. Although central North Atlantic is a significant contributor for non-ARs as well, equally significant moisture is attributed from

the Celtic and North Seas. In contrast to AR events, non-AR precipitation has remote moisture coming from Arctic and subarctic regions such as Greenland, Canadian Arctic, Labrador and Baltic Seas.

Adjacent moisture sources may play a bigger role than it is found in this study for both AR and non-AR events. One limitation of numerical weather models is that they consistently underestimate the MLD during low-pressure or cyclonic systems. Since these precipitation events occur during low-pressure systems, it is likely that the PBL depth increases, and more moisture is mixed during transport at higher geopotential heights. Another reason could be because PBL thresholds assumed in this study underestimates the PBL top during these low-pressure systems near Ireland, which leads to more above-PBL moisture attributions for the trajectories.

Lastly, for AR events, the central and eastern North Atlantic influence can be explained by other studies, where it was discovered that while the transport of moisture from the tropics and sub-tropics were enhanced during landfalling ARs, the precipitable water is largely from adjacent regions (Dacre et al., 2015; Sodemann and Stohl, 2013). This is because much of the tropical/sub-tropical moisture arriving through ARs gets mixed above the boundary layer and can be found in mid to higher altitudes, nearer to the top of the AR (Dacre et al., 2015; Sodemann and Stohl, 2013) This leads to newer moisture pickup and storage in the lower levels of the ARs, and during precipitation these newer moisture fractions are prevalent.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study identifies 1600 landfalling AR events over the 20-year period and 169 country-wide extreme precipitation events in Ireland. Over 80% of the precipitation events are associated with AR occurrences. Top 5 AR and non-AR precipitation events are selected to conduct HYSPLIT-based backward trajectories analysis. As a last step, moisture sources and sinks are analysed using the Sodemann (2008) Lagrangian moisture diagnostic methodology. Results showed the influence of central and eastern North Atlantic moisture towards AR and non-AR precipitation to be the largest in Ireland. While non-ARs have larger influences from nearby Celtic, Irish, and North Seas, AR events source moisture from remote regions such as the north-central Pacific and the sub-tropical North Atlantic.

Further studying the relation between circulation patterns, AR frequency, and associated NAO index in Ireland can improve regional forecasting. This will increase the understanding of extreme precipitation events and add another layer to understand return periods and annual exceedance probability estimations under a changing climate. To initiate these studies, the starting point will be to conduct a climatological study to correlate moisture sources and sinks to general circulation patterns, precipitation amounts, and AR occurrences.

Due to large-scale air circulation patterns and weather regimes, the moisture sources and sinks of ARs can vary drastically. Ireland is an important region to study AR moisture as it is an early rainout region as the remote and near moisture is mixed and brought to west coast of Europe. A newer way to study AR water and verify back-trajectory analysis is stable water isotope-based investigations. High-resolution water isotope studies are expected to reveal further evidence of moisture sources and sink regions, inter-annual, and inter-seasonal variability of ARs.

ARs and extreme precipitation correlations in Ireland alone elucidate the need for accurate forecasting and further investigations of AR-related moisture transport. Irish policymakers and authorities can learn from AR affected regions such as Western California, who are at risk of flooding and water reservoir failures due to AR-induced heavy precipitation totals and short-intense rainfall events. Furthermore, as North Atlantic sea-surface temperatures show record-breaking rise (Johnson et al., 2025), the atmosphere is set to hold more moisture in this region and feed ARs, and that may increase intense AR occurrences in Ireland. It is therefore imperative that Irish authorities heavily invest in building nature-based flood mitigation measures such as peatland restoration, floodplain reconnections, and other runoff attenuation features.

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